

OSCILLATION PARAMETERS STATUS AND PROSPECTS

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ELUCIDATING THE MYSTERIES OF NEUTRINOS

“Neutrinos come in three types, or “flavors,” which undergo quantum **oscillations**. Although the Standard Model can be augmented to accommodate neutrino mass and oscillations, we do not know in which specific way to extend the model. Moreover, different extensions make vastly different predictions about the birth of the universe. **We must further investigate the mysteries of neutrinos in order to explore the deep connections between their physics and the Standard Model.**”

2023 P5 Report

WHAT DO WE KNOW ABOUT NEUTRINO OSCILLATIONS?

- There is a non-zero probability of detecting a different neutrino flavor than that produced at the source:

$$P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = \left| \sum_j U_{\beta j}^* e^{-i \frac{m_j^2 L}{2E}} U_{\alpha j} \right|^2$$

- Where the mixing matrix has 3 mixing angles and one phase (ignoring Majorana):

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta_{23} & \sin \theta_{23} \\ 0 & -\sin \theta_{23} & \cos \theta_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{13} & 0 & \sin \theta_{13} e^{-i\delta} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta_{13} e^{i\delta} & 0 & \cos \theta_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_{12} & \sin \theta_{12} & 0 \\ -\sin \theta_{12} & \cos \theta_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Atmospheric + Accelerator
L/E 500 km/GeV

Reactor + Accelerator
L/E 500 km/GeV

Solar + Reactor
L/E 15,000 km/GeV

As in the quark case, the CP phase can be non-zero if all 3 angles are non-zero.

HOW WELL DO WE KNOW IT?

known to
circa:

- (5%)
- (1.2%)
- (4%)
- (2.4%)
- (2.7%)

- ✦ Most mixing angles and mass differences have been measured using more than one experimental technique.

WHAT DO WE NOT KNOW?

- ✦ **Mass ordering is NOT known for atmospheric neutrinos but known for the solar mass scale.**
- ✦ **The octant of the large mixing angle is not known!**
- ✦ **CP violation in the lepton sector has NOT been measured.**

REACTOR AND ACCELERATOR AS WELL AS ATMOSPHERIC NEUTRINO EXPERIMENTS SEEK TO ANSWER THESE!

HOW WELL DO WE WANT TO KNOW IT?

3 neutrino paradigm

- Measuring the elements of the matrix with more than one technique is essential to paint the full picture of oscillations.

HOW WELL DO WE WANT TO KNOW IT?

One of the three leptonic unitarity triangles of the mixing matrix with unitarity imposed.
 1σ , 90%, 2σ , 99%, 3σ CL (2 dof) allowed regions of the third vertex are drawn.

NOVA AND T2K: THE CURRENT GENERATION OF LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS

- These LBL experiments use neutrino beams produced by accelerators: **NuMI** and **JPARC**
- Precision is achieved by placing a detector close to the source (Near Detector) and one at or close to the oscillation maximum (Far Detector).

$$ND(\nu_\mu) = \Phi(E_\nu) \times \sigma(E_\nu, A) \times \epsilon_{ND}$$

$$FD(\nu_\mu) = \Phi(E_\nu) \times \sigma(E_\nu, A) \times \epsilon_{FD} \times P_{osc}$$

- The measured spectrum in the ND is used to make a prediction of the expectation at the FD before considering oscillations.

Muon neutrino disappearance and electron neutrino appearance is the signature of oscillations

NOVA AND T2K: DIFFERENT ENERGIES

- Experiments are located off-axis for narrow-band, highly pure muon (anti-) neutrino beam:
 - T2K: from J-PARC at 0.6 GeV beam neutrino energy.
 - NOvA: from Fermilab NuMI at 2 GeV beam neutrino energy.
- Different neutrino energy leads to qualitatively different neutrino interactions:
 - T2K: primarily quasi-elastic interactions.
 - NOvA: mix of quasi-elastic, 2p2h, resonant and DIS interactions.

NOVA AND T2K: DIFFERENT BASELINES

- Matter effects modify the spectrum depending on mass ordering, neutrino/anti-neutrino.
- Effect is larger for longer baseline.

	T2K	NOvA
L (baseline)	295 km	810 km
Energy (beam peak)	0.6 GeV	2 GeV
Matter effect*	$\sim \pm 9\%$	$\sim \pm 19\%$
CP effect*	$\sim \pm 30\%$	$\sim \pm 25\%$

*calculated at beam peak energy

NOVA AND T2K COMPLEMENTARITY

- T2K measurements isolate the impact of CP violation whereas NOvA has significant mass ordering sensitivity.
- The complementarity between the experiments has the power to break degeneracies.

NOVA AND T2K INDIVIDUAL RESULTS

- When comparing the allowed the electron neutrino and antineutrino appearance rates, the two experiments have mild preferences for different mass ordering/CP violation combinations.

Results from NOvA and T2K with 2020 data

NOVA AND T2K INDIVIDUAL RESULTS CIRCA 2020

- Mild disagreement (at 90% CL) on allowed CP values in Normal Ordering
- Good agreement on allowed values for Inverted Ordering.

Results from NOvA and T2K with 2020 data

NOVA+T2K RESULTS: MIXING ANGLES

and the reactor neutrino data disambiguation

- Joint fit result is consistent in θ_{13} with reactor experiment results but has degeneracy in θ_{23} .
- Using the θ_{13} PDG average from the reactor experiments lifts degeneracy and provides small preference for the upper octant.

Using reactor constraint on θ_{13} in all other results

NOVA+T2K RESULTS: MASS ORDERING

and the reactor neutrino data disambiguation

- The experiments individually have preferences for normal ordering.
- The NOvA-T2K joint fit has a weak preference for the Inverted Ordering.

NOvA – T2K – w/ reactor	
Bayes factor	1.36 Inverted Ordering/Normal Ordering ~58% : ~42% posterior

• Including the Δm^2 constraint from the Daya Bay reverses the mass ordering preference back to the Normal Ordering.

NOVA+T2K RESULTS: CP VIOLATION

- Normal Ordering allows for a broad range of δ_{CP} .
- Inverted Ordering, CP conserving values lie outside the 3-sigma credible interval.
- $\delta_{CP} = \pi/2$ lies outside 3-sigma credible interval for both mass orderings.

WHAT ABOUT MORE RECENT NOVA AND T2K DATA?

- The joint NOvA and T2K result is based on data accumulated through 2020 for both experiments and were recently published in Nature.
- NOvA has analyzed additional neutrino beam running reaching a 10-years of data milestone.
- T2K has also analyzed additional data and also combined their data with SuperK atmospheric data.
- Both experiments continually improve their analysis methods, updating underlying models, adding new data sets, and more.

NOvA+T2K Nature vol 646, p 818–824 (2025)
T2K+SuperK Phys.Rev.Lett. 134 (2025) 1, 011801

NOVA RESULTS: MASS DIFFERENCE

- Driven by muon neutrino disappearance, NOvA makes the most precise (1.5%) single experiment measurement of the mass difference.
- Mild preference of the upper octant due to reactor constraint.

NOVA RESULTS: MASS ORDERING AND CP VIOLATION

- No strong asymmetry in the rates of appearance. Disfavor combinations which would produce asymmetry.

Exclude IO $\delta_{CP} = \frac{\pi}{2}$ at $> 3\sigma$

Disfavour NO $\delta_{CP} = -\frac{\pi}{2}$ at $\sim 2\sigma$

Normal ordering with Bayes Factor 3.2, 76% odds (frequentist significance 1.4σ).

T2K RESULTS: MASS ORDERING, CP VIOLATION AND OCTANT

- For CP phase, large region excluded at 3σ . CP-conservation values excluded at 90% CL.
- Weak preference for the normal ordering.

- Very weak preference for upper octant when combined with reactor. Close to maximal mixing.

MASS ORDERING AND CP VIOLATION

State of the art circa early 2026

- NO continues to show mild discrepancy between NOvA and T2K/SK.
- IO consistent across all experiments/combinations.
- **Knowing the ordering will tell us which of these scenarios we live in.**

(NOT SO) FUTURE REACTOR EXPERIMENT: JUNO

- 3 sigma mass ordering sensitivity at ~6 years of running (with TAO, a reference detector).

- Incredible precision ($<0.5\%$ in 6 years) for both mass differences (solar and atmospheric).

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS

- ✦ Higher intensity beams and larger mass to collect more neutrinos.
- ✦ High detector resolution for better background rejection.
- ✦ Highly capable near detectors to constrain systematic uncertainties from detector, flux and cross section.

- Complementary programs in the US and Japan:
 - **very long** vs **shorter** baseline (different matter effects!)
 - **on axis** with broadband vs **off-axis** with narrow band beam

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS: HYPER-K

- Resolution in $\sin^2\theta_{23}$ achievable between 0.4 and 2% depending on true value. Most challenging if maximal.
- Ultimate resolution possible $\sim 0.4\%$ in Δm^2_{32} .

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS: DUNE

- In most favorable scenario DUNE has a 5σ significance for mass ordering discovery in 1 year of the first phase of the experiment. Least favorable in 5 years.
- If the scenario (NO, LO) from atmospheric data is chosen, DUNE reaches 5σ no matter what.

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS: DUNE AND HYPER-K

- Ultimate resolution to δ_{CP} is between 5-16°; best at 0 and π because at oscillation maximum we measure $\sin(\delta)$.
- Hyper-K has better resolution at 0 due to higher peak statistics; DUNE has better resolution at $\pm\pi/2$ due to broader spectrum away from oscillation maximum.

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS: DUNE

- DUNE can measure oscillation parameters per bin in a broadband beam.
- If 3-flavor framework is correct, data should prefer the same point in every bin.
- New physics would likely distort observation as a function of L/E .

For more on new physics and beyond 3-flavor framework, see talks later today by Jacobo Lopez Pavon and Mark Ross-Lonergan

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE AND REACTOR EXPERIMENTS

- JUNO and DUNE/Hyper-K will be measuring the atmospheric mass splitting and θ_{13} with comparable resolution.
 - JUNO's current resolution with data already acquired should be comparable to $\text{NO}\nu\text{A}$.
- These measurements are from different processes which are sensitive to different matrix elements.
- The mixing angles are equivalent only if unitarity is assumed.

SUMMARY

- We are in a very interesting scenario where the **yet-to-be determined parameters of neutrino physics** need disambiguation while at the same time they are clearly **within reach**.
- Multiple major neutrino experiments have either begun or will be data-taking soon: JUNO, HyperK and DUNE. **We need them all!**
- The complementarity of these experiments will lead us not only to **discovery of the unknown parameters** but allow us to **stress-test** our understanding of the **3-flavor neutrino oscillation paradigm**.
- We are **entering the precision era of neutrino physics** and it is going to be really exciting!

A nighttime photograph of the Tower Bridge in London, illuminated with purple lights. The bridge spans the River Thames. In the background, the Shard skyscraper is visible, lit up against the dark sky. The city lights are reflected in the water.

Backup

MEASURING OSCILLATION PARAMETERS IN LONG BASELINE EXPERIMENTS

- Leading order dependence on $\sin^2 2\theta_{23}$. Little power to distinguish octant.
- Leading order dependence on $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$. Does not depend on mass ordering.

- Leading order dependence on $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ and $\sin^2 \theta_{23}$. **Can separate octant.**
- Sub-leading order dependence on $\sin^2 2\theta_{13}$ and $\sin^2 2\theta_{23}$. **Can detect CP violation.**
- Sub-leading order dependence on $|\Delta m_{32}^2|$ through matter effect. **Can measure mass ordering.**

FUTURE LONG-BASELINE EXPERIMENTS: HYPER-K

- Resolution in $\sin^2\theta_{23}$ achievable between 0.4 and 2% depending on true value. Most challenging if maximal.
- Ultimate resolution possible $\sim 0.4\%$ in Δm^2_{32} .
- Exclude incorrect mass ordering at $4-5\sigma$ in 10 years depending $\sin^2\theta_{23}$.
- Discovery of CPV at 5σ CL for $\sim 50\%$ of values in 5 years and $\sim 60\%$ in 10 years.

T2K+SUPERK RESULTS: MASS ORDERING, CP VIOLATION AND OCTANT

- CP-conservation values excluded at $\sim 2\sigma$.
- Limited preference for the normal ordering, excluding IO at 1.2σ .

- No octant preference since T2K+reactor and SK prefer different octants.

FUTURE REACTOR EXPERIMENT: JUNO

- Flux peaked at the oscillation maximum for the "solar" mixing angle θ_{12} .
- The "atmospheric" parameters are responsible for the wiggles in the spectrum.
 - The frequency corresponds to Δm_{31}^2 and the phase provides the mass ordering.

- Challenging measurement requires a 3% energy resolution at 1 MeV.

NOVA AND T2K SYSTEMATIC UNCERTAINTIES

- Both analyses approaches reduce systematic uncertainties from over 10% to ~4-5%.
- Demonstrated no need to correlate systematic uncertainties at this exposure. Except for fully correlating systematic uncertainty in ν_e/ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_e/\bar{\nu}_\mu$ cross sections.
- Evaluated robustness against a range of potential neutrino interaction mismodeling.

THE DATA

- Using both experiments data roughly doubles the total statistics at the far detectors.
- The data from both experiments is described well by the joint fit, posterior predictive p-value of 0.75.
- Individual experimental models are used with shared oscillation parameters in a unified framework for statistical inference.

Channel	NOvA	T2K
ν_e	82	94 (ν_e) 14 ($\nu_e 1\pi$)
$\bar{\nu}_e$	33	16
ν_μ	211	318
$\bar{\nu}_\mu$	105	137

T2K: Eur. Phys. J. C (2023) 83: 782

NOvA: Phys. Rev. D 106, 032004 (2022)

Complete sets in backup

2024 NOVA ANALYSIS UPGRADES

Doubled the neutrino data set!

- Added electron neutrino data below 1 GeV where there is additional shape difference albeit with low statistics.

- Improved neutron related and other uncertainties due to detector response.

NOVA+T2K RESULTS: MIXING ANGLES

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NOVA AND T2K ANALYSES

- The experiments have different analyses approaches driven by contrasting experimental design. We also use different neutrino interaction models.

